

Toolkit 2: A toolkit to assess the transferability of evidence produced in other jurisdictions and decision-making levels

Objective of toolkit:

A number of hospital contextual factors are able to affect the extent to which health technologies are capable of producing their effects on hospital performance. HTA is frequently carried out in other settings, such as in institutional bodies, research centres, other healthcare organizations, bringing hospitals to use its evidence without contextualizing it within its specific organizational boundaries. This toolkit provides guidance in systematizing those contextual variables that can affect the concrete implementation of health technologies and, in turn, their impact on hospital performance.

The toolkit is to be intended as an assessment of the overall adequacy of the organizational context in the implementation of a *specific* health technology. Therefore, this analysis should be repeated in all circumstances in which a costly technology must be assessed. The overall framework of the toolkit, though, can be further extended to general considerations on hospitals' readiness to implement technology use.

Domains of relevant contextual factors:

Hospital infrastructure and architecture

Hospital's availability of financial resources

Leadership styles

Human resource management tools

Transferability issues:

External validity:

Can results be transferred to other organisations or cross-border to other healthcare systems?

The focus is on the organizational dimension. Results can be transferred to hospitals with similar characteristics, but each hospital is likely to have a unique mix of characteristics and is encouraged to perform this analysis individually.

Can results be transferred to the use of other technologies?

The toolkit is built based on the relationships detected for different types of health technologies. Therefore, its validity is held to cover a broad range of technologies. Its intended use, though, is related to specific technologies assessed individually or in similar groups, therefore results cannot be extended to technologies with very different characteristics.

Methods for data collection:

Hospital contextual factors can be assessed through the following data collection methods:

Hospital webpages and official ministerial/regional online documents can provide information on general structural information such as ownership, architectural type of hospital, number of beds etc. Additional information, such as number of discharges, number of consultations etc., can be found through *clinical records and other organizational records*. Information such as, for example, the hospital's role in a network, level of integration of ICT tools, hospital's budgeting system, organizational chart and patient pooling approaches can be assessed through *interviews to top managerial figures*. Other more specific items can be assessed through *interviews to key managerial figures*. For example, HTA activities can be described by the Head of the HTA unit or by a clinical director; ICT tools regularly used can be described by the responsible of ICT; job, people and performance evaluation activities can be described by the Human Resource Management Director. Finally, further data can be gathered through *surveys and questionnaires to staff*. Staff, for example, can provide evidence about the leadership styles they experience and their perception on decision-making processes.

Data collection and interpretation:

Each item provided in this toolkit should be assessed through the adequate source of detection. For each, one out of five possible evaluations should be defined:

- Strong enabler to the use of technology
- Weak enabler to the use of technology
- Neutral to the use of technology
- Weak Barrier to the use of technology
- Weak Barrier to the use of technology

In order to define each evaluation, a qualitative assessment must be carried out following the main directives presented in the description of each item.

The online Toolkit is available at:

<https://altems.unicatt.it/altems-ricerca-a-toolkit-to-assess-the-transferability-of-evidence-produced-in-other-jurisdictions>